

1st International Conference
on
**Latest Innovations in Sustainable Engineering and Technology
Management**

ICLISETM-2021 PROCEEDINGS

Date 26th February 2021

Organized by

United Technical College, Bharatpur, Metropolitan City 11, Chitwan, Nepal

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For Individual articles; As given in abstracts

Know Your Host

United Technical College, College of Engineering, popularly known as (U-TEC), was established in 2008 (2065 BS) under private sector initiative. The foundation of U-TEC was instigated by a group of farsighted professionals and academicians who comprehended the need of a college for offering the technical education outside the valley. Mostly, the university level engineering education in private sector was concentrated in the capital only. Therefore, for reaching a wider section of Nepali youth outside the valley and making the quality technical education accessible and affordable to the poor and deprived youths in outer region, it was essential to establish technical colleges outside the capital, which U-TEC did by establishing the first private engineering college in Chitwan. Since its establishment, the youths from outside the valley region have taken full advantage and are continually enrolling in different engineering disciplines offered by the college. Since the establishment the college has produced six batches of undergraduate engineers so far in Civil Engineering and three in Electrical & Electronics Engineering.

The facility at U-TEC is located in Bharatpur Metropolitan City, Ward No.-11, Bhojad, U-TEC Chowk, Chitwan. It has physical and institutional resources built on 20 Ropanis (1.0 ha) of land. These resources essentially cater to the academic needs in the bachelor level programs. The full-time Bachelor of Civil Engineering, Computer Engineering and Electrical & Electronics Engineering degree offered by U-TEC, affiliated to Pokhara University, builds skill, expertise, and knowledge among its graduates in the area of higher technology and design. The industry driven project works, research and development and learning outlined by the university is followed strictly to enhance the academic quality. So, UTEC provides unconditional opportunities for graduates to pursue engineering education with passion and confidence.

Vision:

The vision of the U-TEC is to move forward as the center of higher education, by improving on intellectual capacity through activities in scientific and technical education, research and outreach.

Serve as valuable resources for fulfilling demand of quality technical human resources in the area of civil services, industry and society; and remain a source of pride for the Nation and contribute in economic growth of the country by producing quality technical human resources.

Mission:

- To provide students best opportunities and environment of learning and help them to attain high level of academic quality, scientific aspiration, technical and self-employment professional competence and skills.
- To prepare and train students to serve the society and the people, enhance the design quality of engineering works and improve the life and to comprehend the need for ethical standards in personal, social and public life.
- To help the students to conduct different types of research in engineering, write research reports and prepare papers for presenting in conferences and seminars in engineering and technology related issues of national and public interest.

- To train the students for providing necessary technical and consultancy services as demanded by the government, private sectors, NGOs and INGOs.
- To enhance the knowledge and practical skills of the students by providing training in latest job-oriented technology.

Objectives:

- To produce engineering human resources in the field of engineering from bachelor to master levels in the various engineering disciplines.
- To conduct different types of research studies, conferences and seminars in the issues of national interests on engineering sectors with mobilizing wide partnership.
- To provide necessary technical and consultancy services as demanded by the Government of Nepal, private sectors, NGOs and INGOs.

Values:

- Academic integrity and accountability.
- Respect and tolerance for the views of every individual.
- Attention to issues of national relevance as well as of global concern.
- Breadth of understanding, including knowledge of the human sciences.
- Appreciation to intellectual excellence and creativity.
- An unfettered spirit of exploration, rationality and enterprise.

Programs Offered

Graduate Program

ID	Course Name	Program	Seats	Length
001	M.Sc. In Construction Management	Masters	15	2 Year

Under Graduate 4-Years B.E. Program (Eligibility: I.Sc. / +2 / Diploma)

ID	Course Name	Program	Seats	Length
001	BE In Civil Engineering	Bachelor	96	4 Year
002	BE. In Electrical & Electronics Engineering	Bachelor	48	4 Year
003	BE. In Computer Engineering	Bachelor	48	4 Year

(Affiliated to Pokhara University)

About the Conference

United Technical College, Chitwan, Nepal warmly welcomes the professionals and researchers/scientists from the field of engineering and technology management to attend the upcoming international conference on recent trends in sustainable engineering and technology management. The conference has been proved as a platform for global networking for the researchers, professionals and executives and business persons around the globe. The event is exciting and memorable with interactive sessions, presentation through online platform. The conference is facilitated by eminent speakers

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Guests

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Message from the Conference President

It is my great pleasure to write that the International Conference on Latest Innovations in Sustainable Engineering and Technology Management (LISE TM, 2021) to be held virtually online on 26 February 2021 by United Technical College of Engineering (U-TEC). This conference has been designed to focus various scientific tracks covering major areas of research in Sustainable Engineering and Technology Management.

The objective of the international conference is to provide opportunities for professionals, academics, researchers, scientists and students from all over the world to come together and learn from each other. LISETM, 2021 aims to accelerate scientific discoveries and major milestones in the current situation, challenges and innovations relating to sustainable Engineering and Technology and also its management.

The LISE TM, 2021 is committed to expand the collaboration with researchers, engineers, scientists and professionals in the field of Engineering and Technology.

Er. Babu Ram Upadhyaya

President

Message from the Conference Vice President

It is pretty heartwarming to note that the United Technical College of Engineering (U-TEC) is hosting its First International E-Conference on Latest Innovations in Sustainable Engineering and Technology Management (LISETM, 2021) on 26th, February 2021.

Putting in order such an event at this point of time strengthens our objective of developing a situation for the exchange of ideas towards innovation in Engineering and Technology Management. I wish the conference would be able to deliberate on current issues of national and international significance, particularly in the field of Building Construction, Highway Engineering, Clean Energy Development, Green Engineering and Technology Management. The committee has received large number of very good quality papers that are to be presented in the conference. I am sure that this occasion will provide a pleasant atmosphere for the researchers and academicians to freely exchange the views and ideas with others. I pass on my warm compliments and felicitations to the organizing committee and the participants and extend my best wishes for the success of the conference.

A handwritten signature in black ink, reading "Awasthi", written over a horizontal line.

Prof. Keshab Datt Awasthi (Ph.D.)

Vice President Organizing Committee

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Asst. Prof. Raju Dhakal (M.E. in Telecommunication)
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(Expertise: Data Communication, Artificial Intelligence)

नेपाल इन्जिनियरिङ्ग परिषद्
(नेपाल इन्जिनियरिङ्ग परिषद् ऐन, २०५५ द्वारा स्थापित)
Nepal Engineering Council
(Estd. Under NECA Act 2055)

Ref: ११०/१०७७-७८/२१८

Foreword

I am pleased to put some words on International Conference, Latest Innovations in Sustainable Engineering & Technology Management that will be held on 26th of February, 2021. These conferences provide a platform to researchers, scientists, engineers and students to enhance their research capabilities through sharing of multidisciplinary ideas amongst experts from different areas.

Nepal Engineering Council (NEC), as a regulatory body, has always advocated the need of research in the field of engineering for the enhancement of students and researchers. I congratulate United Technical College; permanently approved by NEC, for organizing the conference. The initiation is really praise-worthy.

I, as a registrar of Nepal Engineering Council would like to thank all the team members for making this fantastic atmosphere for all to express their views and learn in the field of sustainable engineering and technology management. Conferences like these are designed to create networking opportunities; they also provide access to the newest ideas and concepts.

I wish all the best to the College and the team-members for their present and future endeavors to motivate researchers.

Er. Khem Raj Joshi
Registrar
Nepal Engineering Council

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Vice President - DKIRF / Global Peace Ambassador - GPF, UAE / Visiting Professor / International
& National Award Winner / Social Activist / Educational Consultant

Date: 21st February 2021

Dear Sir/Madam,

Greetings from Dr. A. Dinesh Kumar,

In this age of rapidly changing technologies, it is essential for all professionals to keep abreast of latest developments. In this regard, the International Conference on Latest Innovations in Sustainable Engineering and Technology Management (LISETM21), Organized by United Technical College, Chitwan, Nepal will provide a platform for the professionals to share their knowledge. The conference will provide an excellent platform to hold discussions and share the new ideas in this important are of research. I am very happy and congratulate the team for organizing this conference and my best wishes for the grand success of conference.

With Regards,

Dr. A. Dinesh Kumar
Vice President

To
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FOREWORD

An innovative application of scientific inventions to solve varieties of problems of human beings in society leads to the development of engineering and technology. It is believed that continuous research and innovations in engineering and technology and managing them systematically can only solve basic (human need based) problems, comfortable (human wants based) problems, and desires (human dream based) problems of society. The systematic management of 21st century Engineering and Technologies include identifying the potential breakthrough technologies and developing them systematically to realize the dreams to take the civilization to its supersaturated level with abilities such as ubiquitous, omni-potent, and immortal super human beings. In this regard, the International Conference on Latest Innovations in Sustainable Engineering and Technology Management is considered the most significant and useful event to elevate the comfortable lifestyle of human beings in the civilized world. Further, information communication and computation technology (ICCT) and its underlying technologies, including artificial intelligence, robotics, IoT, cloud computing, 3D-printing, virtual and augmented realities, and Nanotechnology are considered as universal general-purpose technologies of the 21st century with potential abilities to solve many problems as one can expect from ideal technology.

I am happy to write this foreword to the Proceedings of International Conference on Latest Innovations in Sustainable Engineering and Technology Management organized by United Technical College, Chitwan, Nepal and is being released today by the untired effort of the Editorial Committee. The Proceedings contains many important introductory and advanced research articles on Innovations in Engineering, Technology and Management of Technology to solve problems in society through advanced design of products and services in primary, secondary, tertiary and quaternary industries which are arranged in such a way as to improve the curiosity of the readers and think innovatively toward further research contributions in the field and future endeavour in society.

Dr. P. S. Aithal

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Vice Chancellor

Srinivas University

Mangalore, Karnataka, India

Date:-22/02/2021

Advanced Research Publications appreciates United Technical College, Chitwan, Nepal for much-needed efforts in advancing research and providing a platform to researchers for engaging and thought-provoking discussions to bring forward innovations through organizing the International Conference on *Latest Innovations in Sustainable Engineering and Technology Management*.

We wish you all a great success and assure our complete support in publishing your quality articles in our Journals and secure your intellectual property.

Once again, we congratulate all participants.

With Regards,

Shalini Tripathi

Director

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Foreword

I am delighted that UNITED TECHNICAL COLLEGE, Nepal is organising International conference on Latest Innovations in Sustainable Engineering and Technology Management (LISETM-2021). This conference highlights (i) **Sustainability** through comprehensive conversation on infrastructure sustainability and resiliency, (ii) **Sharing** the latest advances in sustainable energy, infrastructure planning, design, and construction, (iii) Meeting Key People for research **Inspiration**, (iv) development of **Networking** with Peers, (v) **Expertise** to scientific community and (vi) Being in business should be rewarding and fun mindset. I, therefore, wish the success on this international event.

Dr Mohammad Abdul Mannan
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Message from Desk of Editor

Dear Sir/Madam

Greetings from Desk of Editor

This is expression of happiness to thank you all for supporting us directly or indirectly. Thank you so much for giving us a chance to create a platform for sharing the best gift that is friendship and knowledge. As [U.S. Army War College](#) introduced the concept VUCA to describe the more Volatile, Uncertain, Complex and Ambiguous multilateral world from 2002 ,the end of the [Cold War](#) . We must strive to develop our Attitude, Skill and Knowledge (ASK) for being few among many in this VUCA world. The speed of change of technology and social needs want us to quickly update ourselves for sustainability. The urgency of investment in brain is most for gain. World bank urges governments to act: for Investment in human capital is most important to develop high-order cognitive and socio behavioural skills in addition to foundational skills. Growing role of technology in life and business means that all types of jobs (including low - skilled ones) require more advanced cognitive skills. Technology changes demand for skills. To prepare for changing nature of work, we must boost investment in brain - most effective way to build valuable skills for future labour markets. COVID 19 has created extra pressure for our market. Hope this conference might have helped each other through our combined efforts.

Once again thank you for your efforts from all stakeholders to make it success. Wish you all a great success and pleasant years to come with a hope to have your cooperation in future. Kindly feel free to contact for publishing your full paper in reputed journals through us.

Thanking you with humble regards.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

About the College.....	iii
About the Conference.....	v
Message from Conference President.....	vii
Message from Conference Vice President.....	viii
Committee members.....	ix
Foreword Messages.....	xiii
Message from Desk of Editor.....	xviii
Table of Contents.....	xix

Paper Abstracts

1. Innovative Management and its Challenges in the Organizations in the Third Millennium Coincided with the Crisis of Corona 1
2. Numerical Simulatin of Dynamic Stall of an Airfoil.....3
3. Prioritization of Storage Hydropower Projects under Study in Nepal.....4
4. Variation Order Impact Assessment of Building Construction Project.....6
5. Assessment of Impact of COVID-19 Lockdown on Nepal's Construction Sector Based on Selected Construction Projects.....8
6. Impact of Mobile and Internet Subscriptions on Revenue of Telecom Service Operator of Nepal.....10
7. Assessment of Community Based Disaster Preparedness After Gorkha Earthquake 2015 in Godawari Municipality of Lalitpur District, Nepal.....11
8. Statistical Model on Impact of Agriculture in Economic Development of Nepal.....13

9. Review of National Road Safety Action Plan 2013-2020.....	14
10. Contractual Performance Assessment of Sikta Irrigation Project, Banke, Nepal.....	16
11. The Challenges in the Implementation of e-Government Services in Province – 1 Nepal.....	18
12. Assessment of Quality Management Practice Adopted in Melamchi Water Treatment Plant Sundarijal, Kathmandu.....	19
13. Assessment of Household Cement Consumption Pattern in Pokhara Metropolitan City..	21
14. Antimicrobial and Antioxidant Properties of Green Synthesized Nanoparticles Against Food Spoiling Microorganisms.....	22
15. Building Code-Byelaws Compliance and Cost Assessment of Private Building Construction of Devdaha Municipality.....	23
16. Possibility of Rooftop Rainwater Harvesting – A Case Study of Kathmandu Valley.....	25
17. Recommendation System Using Collaborative Filtering Algorithm for the Movie Recommendations.....	27
18. MRI-based Brain Tumor Segmentation using Convolutional Neural Networks.....	28
19. Assessment of Road and Bridge project Performance in terms of Time - Cost.....	29
20. Building Byelaws and Building Code Compliance in High-rise Apartment Buildings in Kathmandu Valley.....	30
21. Quality Management Practice on construction of Suncity Apartment at Kathmandu.....	32
22. SiConSofa - A precast Concrete Block for using Drain and Retention Wall.....	34
23. Technology and the Environment – A Framework for a Symbiotic Relationship	35
Supporters.....	36

Innovative Management and its Challenges in the Organizations in the Third Millennium Coincided with the Crisis of Corona

Dr. Hamid Saremi
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Abstract

In the third millennium, particularly in the current crisis caused by Corona, which is a far-fetched phenomenon of the present age, that its effects changed the shape of businesses, and managers' organizations and enterprises were forced to resort to innovative methods to manage this critical period and use new technology and tools; So everyone wanted to find a way to save their job.

In the current context, the Corona outbreak, society and the economy, and consequently organizations and companies, has reached a level that has led to innovative methods and new techniques. Therefore, due to such cases, the world has faced increasing technological changes with many complexities. Speed of science production make the future to face challenges and unknowns in all areas.

This global transformation affects the political, economic, social and cultural systems and changes the management. The impact of managers' influence on human resources, their tendencies and the promotion of productivity will also be different. Managers must be prepared and able to make accurate decisions, innovative strategies and future planning. Because managers in the third millennium will face a mysterious world that needs innovation and rapid change.

Companies overtake themselves with planning, strategies, and policies of creative and innovative managers. Perhaps the decision of managers to have an astonishing effect on organizations, Predictability in work also originates from the principle of futurism is one of the characteristics of creative and innovative managers. Accordingly, managers should prioritize the three factors of foresight, innovation, and quality excellence in achieving success.

Innovation is one of the factors that play a very important role in developing and solving problems inside and outside the organization. Therefore, organizations that are thinking of surviving in the competitive market, pay special attention and sensitivity to this concept and try to institutionalize creative thinking and innovation in the organization and give importance to them.

But there are always obstacles and challenges to creative and innovative thinking that people fail to achieve due to ignorance or inattention to these obstacles. At the same time, the mere absence of obstacles does not lead to creative thinking in the organization; rather, it encourages managers to use this thinking as a driving force in moving towards creative ideas and innovation.

**International Conference on Latest Innovations in Sustainable Engineering and Technology Management
LISETM21**

This paper studies innovation and innovative management and its challenges in the third millennium, especially in the context of the global crisis caused by the corona virus.

Keywords: *Third Millennium, Management, Innovation, Globalization, Foresight, Corona Crisis, Organization*

How to Cite

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Numerical Simulation of Dynamic Stall of an Airfoil

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Abstract

The S809 airfoil model was simulated using the software FLUENT 6.0 to compute for Steady State Case and Dynamic Stall Process (Unsteady Case). The computed results were compared to the experimental data and the aerodynamic performance was analyzed. Secondly, dynamic stall process or Unsteady State flow around the airfoil was simulated using $k-\omega$ SST turbulence model with added transitional flow. Light Stall case of $8^{\circ}\pm 5.5^{\circ}$ and Deep Stall case of $20^{\circ}\pm 10^{\circ}$ were simulated. The results obtained were different in both cases. During the deep stall, the appearance of leading edge vortex and induced second vortex caused the flow structure to be different from the light stall. The steady state and unsteady state cases were found to be quite different. As the chosen airfoil is from the thicker airfoil family, the flow starts to separate from the trailing edge in the both steady and unsteady case. In the steady case, the generated vortex moves towards the leading edge. Whereas in the unsteady case, although the vortex is formed firstly at the trailing edge but with the increase in angle of attack there is the appearance of leading edge vortex. With the further increase in angle of attack, there are other secondary vortices shedding from the leading edge. During pitching down process, the vortex reduces in size and it slowly moves towards the trailing edge and flow finally attaches to the surface of the airfoil.

Keywords: *Dynamic Stall, Numerical Computation, Turbulence Model, S809.*

How to Cite

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Prioritization of Storage Hydropower Projects under Study in Nepal

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Abstract

Nepal is rich in water resources. Nepal has huge potential to generate energy but the country is still suffering from energy crisis till date. The major crisis is during the dry season. This energy stricken scenario can be reduced by accelerating development of storage hydropower projects. Due to the lack of political stability and managerial expertise on hydropower sectors, any hydropower projects are hardly completed on time in Nepal. This research aims to find out the factors hindering the storage hydropower projects and prioritize the storage hydropower projects of Nepal.

The study has covered six major storage hydropower projects that are under study. Uttarganga Storage Hydroelectric Project and Budigandaki Storage Hydroelectric Project are located in Gandaki Province. Dudhkoshi Storage Hydroelectric Project and Tamor Storage Hydroelectric Project lie in Province 1 while Nalsaugad Storage Hydroelectric Project lies in Karnali Province. These all projects are in the stage of feasibility study.

The methodology of research followed Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP) based on Multi Criteria Decision Making (MCDM). Literature review was done with AHP application in different sector including hydropower. Besides this, reviews were done on aspects like energy crisis, present energy status and future demand. Likewise pair wise comparison was done in different multiple criteria. Additionally, response from client and expertise opinion were conducted.

Technical, financial, environmental, policy and political uncertainties and responses from the project personnel were the major criteria that can affect the priority of the storage hydropower projects. Among the factors, Technical Factor was given the highest importance to be considered for the development of storage hydropower project. The findings of the research revealed that Nalsaugad Storage Hydropower Project to be the best on the basis of the multi criteria considered. The sensitivity analysis with respect to factors was done, which shows no significant difference in the ranking of projects at base case and at the case of change in weight of factors.

This research is expected to assist by project managers, project directors, and concerned government authorities in prioritizing the storage projects of Nepal.

Keywords: Analytical Hierarchal Process (AHP), Integrated Nepal Power System (INPS)

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Variation Order Impact Assessment of Building Construction Project

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Abstract

Variation orders consist of the additions, omissions, alterations and substitution in terms of quality, quantity and schedule of works. The main objective of this study is to identify the origin and causes of variation orders and their impacts in project cost and completion time. The study is conducted in project inside Tribhuvan University premises, Kathmandu and the status of variation orders, causes and impacts in project cost and time is analyzed to develop measures which can be beneficial in upcoming similar projects.

The primary data were collected from the questionnaire survey and field study. For the case study of the project, contract documents, final bill and project related documents were obtained from the related offices which were thoroughly studied to obtain the project related findings about variation orders relating to project cost and completion time. Five ranking Likert scales have been used for ranking the perception based relative importance index of respondents about causes of variation orders.

Existence of variation orders inside Tribhuvan University premises, Kathmandu has been noted from the study. 9.85%, 5.99%, 10.37%, 12.32% and 21.02% cost above the contract amount has been incurred at the completion of the projects respectively. Similarly, 26.67%, 83.33%, 12.5%, 20% and 25% time for the successive contract has been increased by the extension of the contract completion time. From the study, main causes of variation orders are known to be change of plan, change of scope, defect of bill of quantities, lack of specified and appropriate competent construction manager and impediment in prompt decision making. Similarly, causes of variation orders impacting project cost are additional work, client financial problems/delay in payment of bill and change in design. Causes of variation orders impacting project time are changes in design, delay in payment and dispute between parties to the contract. The control measures for the variation orders are appointment of project manager to supervise design, preparation of bill of quantities with good estimate based on proper detailed drawings and adequate financial planning.

Keywords: *Variation, Design, Delay, Client, Consultant, Dispute, Supervision*

Acknowledgements

I express my sincere gratitude to my supervisors Prof. Dr. Sateesh Kumar Ojha and Prof. Dr. Madhav Prasad Koirala for their continuous support and valuable guidance.

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Assessment of Impact of COVID-19 Lockdown on Nepal's Construction Sector Based on Selected Construction Projects

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Abstract

Corona virus disease 2019 (COVID-19), a global pandemic as declared by World Health Organization (WHO) is causing severe impacts in almost all aspects of life in Nepal. In response to this pandemic, Nepal Government announced country-wide lockdown from 24th March, 2020 and ended on 21st July, 2020.

Corona virus pandemic is an unprecedented event affecting almost every aspects of construction sector in Nepal. Hence, this study was carried out to assess the impact of COVID-19 lockdown on Nepal's construction sector based on selected construction projects. For this purpose, case study of five ongoing construction projects was taken into account and questionnaires were distributed to responsible officials (client, consultant and contractor) of those projects.

This study intended to find out impact of COVID-19 lockdown on: supply-demand trend analysis; cost and time of construction projects. Besides, this study also intends to find the contractual issues and claims associated with COVID-19 lockdown.

The study reveals that COVID-19 caused serious disruption on supply chain, project cost and time increases due to uncertainty regarding availability of subcontractors/suppliers/labor. Impact, however differs on the nature, scale and size of the project. Besides, study also implies that contractual disputes are likely to increase due to lockdown. Each contract and its conditions have to be carefully analyzed to determine a party's specific entitlement.

There is uncertainty as to when the situation becomes normal and construction work can be carried out with optimum efficiency.

Keywords: *Construction, Contractual issues, COVID-19, Impact, Lockdown*

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This research was supported by Department of Civil Engineering, Central Campus, Pulchowk, Institute of Engineering, Tribhuvan University. I would like to express my deepest gratitude and appreciation to my supervisor Asst. Prof. Santosh Kumar Shrestha for his invaluable guidance, supervision, encouragement, support, advice and insight in the commencement of this research to its conclusion. His suggestion and support to complete this research are extremely appreciable. I would also like to express my thanks to M.Sc.in Construction Management Faculty and Program Coordinator Asst. Prof. Mahendra Raj Dhital, Department of Civil Engineering for providing moral support and valuable feedback during thesis work. I am indebted to Mr. Sanjeev Koirala, Managing Partner, Claims and Dispute Resolution Consultancy (CRDC) Pvt. Ltd and all other members of CDRC Pvt. Ltd. for providing me the required data to carry out this research. Besides, I would also like to thank Mr. Badri Dhungana, Consultant

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Engineer of HPPCL (Herbs Production and Processing Co. Ltd.) Building for his cooperation and support. Moreover, I would also like to thank Dr. Anjaya Kumar Mishra for his help and encouragement. In addition to that, I am thankful to all those who sincerely participate in the questionnaire survey. Last but not the least, I am very grateful to my family and friends for their direct/indirect support and encouragement throughout this research work

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Impact of Mobile and Internet Subscriptions on Revenue of Telecom Service Operators of Nepal

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Abstract

Nepal, together with the world witnessed growth in mobile subscriptions from 0 to 126% and internet subscriptions from 0% to 80% in less than two-decades. Integration of voice telephony over the Internet through VoIP (Voice over Internet Protocol) technology had resulted to develop several OTT (over the top) services like skype, Viber, WhatsApp, Messenger to replace the voice telephony and its' revenue. This has a great impact on revenue of telecommunications service operators from domestic as well as International calls. This paper analyzed the panel data of mobile and internet subscriptions of Nepal for more than a decade period and regressed with the composite GDP (Transport, storage, and Communications) of the same year. This research found that 1% growth of mobile tele-density has positive impact on GDP (Transport, storage and communication) by 1.3627%;while 1% growth in internet tele-density has negative impact on the same GDP by 2.7394%. This research has implications to telecommunications service operators and exchequer where they need to look for new avenues of revenue clubbed with internet applications to sustain revenue and business in changed scenario.

Keywords: *mobile subscriptions, internet subscriptions, VoIP, OTT services, GDP, telecom business*

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Assessment of Community Based Disaster Preparedness After Gorkha Earthquake 2015 in Godawari Municipality of Lalitpur District, Nepal

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Abstract

The study on the Assessment of Community Based Disaster Preparedness after Gorkha Earthquake 2015 in Godawari Municipality of Lalitpur District, Nepal was conducted during the period from August 2019 to February 2020 in Godawari Municipality, Lalitpur. The main objective of this study was to find out the preparedness status of the individual in the community after 2015 earthquake. In this study secondary literatures were received from various sources such as published reports, papers, manuals and published and unpublished thesis. Field observation, in-depth interview and questionnaire survey were used as the instruments for the field study. The study found out that preparedness activities have been practiced by the individuals. After 2015 earthquake most of the people are aware and prepared for having safe house from the next strong earthquake occurrence. People have started preparing for basic needs, logistic planning, spending for safer house and family. Maximum number of respondents have prepared basic needs followed by inspecting houses for further maintenance, saving money, logistic planning i.e. where to go and how to contact. In addition to this saving money, doing insurance of the house and lives are some of the new things they have started adopting. It is known that around 45% of the individuals prepared on having safe house. However, most of the population (64%) do not have knowledge about earthquake preparedness. The study would like to suggest that earthquake preparedness knowledge program should be conducted in the community by the municipality as well as social organization. An individual who have got knowledge should share their knowledge regarding earthquake preparedness. A public awareness program should be conducted by the municipality and ward office in order to make the society cope with the further risk of earthquake.

Keywords: *Earthquake, Community Based Disaster Preparedness, Field Observation, in-depth interview, Questionnaire Survey, Insurance, Logistic Planning.*

Acknowledgements

I would like to extend my sincere thanks to Prof. Dr. Nar Bikram, faculties for providing their valuable comments during the study and all the LIAST family. I would like to express my deepest appreciation to the respondents and the Godawari Municipality Mayor, Municipality Staffs and representatives of humanitarian organizations and interviewees. I would also like to thank my family as well as my friends for their cooperation.

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Statistical Model on Impact of Agriculture in Economic Development of Nepal

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Abstract

Nepal has many factors that influence the economic development one of the factor is agriculture. In Nepal, over the last fifteen years poverty has remarkably come down in spite of lower economic growth meaning that reducing poverty would be much easier if economic growth rate could be increased. Regarding economic growth contribution of agriculture sector to GDP is gradually decreasing every year, while that of non- agriculture sector increasing. The contribution of agriculture sector to GDP is estimated to stand 27.0 % and 73.0 % respectively in the FY 2018/19 while their contribution during FY 2017/18 was 28.1% and 71.9% respectively.

Keywords: *Statistical Model, Agriculture, Economic Development, GDP*

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Review of National Road Safety Action Plan 2013-2020

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Abstract

Road Safety is a pertinent national issue with 2,255 road traffic fatalities occurs in 2076-77. Nepal in compliance with global commitment in accordance with the United Nations Decade of Action for Road Safety 2011-2020 as, had prepared their own Road safety action plan (2013-2020) with target of reducing 50% road fatalities by end of 2020. The action plan had been formulated in five different pillars with assigned responsible stakeholders with well-defined activities. The road fatalities of 1,610 at 2010 rises to 2,255(Value is on lower side due to covid impact) in 2020, will is not as accordance with the target set. Poor database system, weak management system, political instability, lack of accountable organization and implementation framework are the reason behind the the current scenario. The existing policies and strategies, institutional arrangement and capacity are reviewed to assess the challenges associated with each proposed activity in the action plan. Despite the increases on road crashes and fatalities, but the rate is decreasing when compared with the registered vehicles. The existing institutional, legal and funding arrangements in Nepal had limited the prioritization of road safety in the country and implementation of activities proposed in the action plan. In a meantime, various positive changes have been made on pillar- 1 Road Safety Management, pillar -2 Safer Roads and mobility; and pillar 3: Safer Vehicles. Road Safety Council is one the verge of finalization, Road Safety Act and other policies are being changed for betterment. Similarly, Road Safety Audit is being undertaken from Department of Road on the completed and under constructed roads, Vehicles and Transport Management Act and Regulation is being amended; vehicles fitness center and Trauma center is being established and had started its operation, Institute of Engineering (Academic institution of Nepal) had launched Road Safety as a curriculum in Bachelor and Master courses to work on capacity building. With federal system, the main challenge is how road safety agenda will be taken at provincial and local government level. There is a need to strengthen the institutional and legal environment in the country in line with the new federal structure to achieve existing goals as well as plan for the next decade of action. The results emphasis on the SWOT analysis of the current action plan and provide the feedback for the betterment on the next action plan with speed being highlight as the vital parameter.

Keywords: *Road Safety Action Plan, Five Pillars, Road Safety Audit*

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Contractual Performance Assessment of Sikta Irrigation Project, Banke, Nepal

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Abstract

Government of Nepal (GoN) is implementing much small, medium and large type of Irrigation Projects. Sikta Irrigation Project (SIP) is the National Pride Project implemented by the Government of Nepal. The command area of the project was 42766.00 ha and beneficiary of the project have 46715 house hold consisting 449588 population of Banke district.

The study is focused to analyses the contractual performance of SIP using Earn Value Analysis for ongoing and status assessment of completed contracts along with the consequences of delay and disputes of selected contracts.

The project consists of 52 no of contracts out of which 14 ongoing contracts were evaluated using EVA & S-curve. All contracts were assessed for delay and dispute resolution of only Papu costal JV, Kathmandu, has been analyzed. The actual expenditure of the project has 16.26 billion (64.90% of estimated cost) and allocated budget was 18.26 billion (72.99% of estimated cost) where as estimated cost has 25.032 billion. It indicates that progress of project was 64.90% and fails to complete the schedule time 2076/077. It was found that trough the contracts were within budget; however the time overrun has server. The overall ongoing project Earn Value was more than Actual value and less than planned value. The average cost variance percentage 2.24%, Cost performance index 1.02, shows the effectiveness of cost in the project due to low bedding of 86% of contracts. Schedule variance percentage is -44.2%, Schedule performance index is 0.55 and average index is 0.785 where less than 1.0. Depending upon condition the estimate to complete and estimate at completion may vary from 1.95 million to 3.54 million and 3.78 million to 5.37 million respectively.

The mean planned duration of the contracts under the study is 18.06 month and mean actual time 34.73 month with standard deviation of 10.00 month and mean time variance is 13.66 month behind the schedule and mean time overrun is 16.66 month .The contracts need to be rectified in terms of time by proper scheduling and resource leveling based local calendar. Hope the new amendments (PPMO 10th) of time extension will be helpful for timely completion of contracts.

Keywords: *Irrigation, disputes, causes of delay, Earn Value, S-curve, cost performance index*

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The Challenges in the Implementation of e-Government Services in Province – 1 Nepal

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Abstract

In the current era of information and communication technologies, it is impossible to have good government without e-government. Nepal, however is also taking its initiative to deliver government services through internet. Development of e-government in developing and least developed countries like Nepal have the potential to make better relationships between government and citizens. This research tries to analyze those difficulties faced by province-1 government and its local bodies. Here the various difficulties with respect to inception of e-based administrations in Province 1 are classified into Financial, Human, Organizational, Technical and Regulatory or Legal and other difficulties. The overall objective of this research is to explore citizen's awareness towards e-Government activities, to find the challenges and obstacles blocking e-Government achievement. Also the critical success factors for effective implementation of e-Government services in the context of Province 1 and its Local Government are studied. This paper majorly depicts the awareness, implementation and associated challenges of e-Government services in terms of improved service delivery. Furthermore the association between variables - awareness, implementation, and challenges were analyzed by determining Pearson's correlation coefficient & scatter diagram which yielded significant result. This research recommends that the government should provide guideline alongside the proper implementation of provincial e-governance interoperability framework to be addressed as soon as possible. We are highly grateful for the technical assistance and valuable supervision from Purbanchal University School of Engineering & Technology (PUSET) department.

Keywords: *e-Government, Local Government, Challenges, Implementation, Province 1*

Acknowledgements

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Assessment of Quality Management Practice Adopted in Melamchi Water Treatment Plant Sundarijal, Kathmandu

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Abstract

Quality Management is a new approach in the construction industries. Quality assurance and quality control are two major elements in quality management important in any construction sector in order to sustain the project in long run, improvement as well as to satisfy the needs of the employer and the end user. The aim of the research was to explore the nature and scope of construction quality practices adopted by Melamchi Water Treatment Plant. Melamchi Drinking Water Supply Project is a national concern project of Nepal with projected cost of US\$ 464 million covers varieties of scope of quality management elements as well as civil engineering works if well documented could serve as a reference for future similar construction projects.

A structured questionnaire survey was used to collect data from Construction Project teams namely; Project Managers, Project Engineers, Site Engineers and Quality Control/Assurance Managers of client, consultant and Contractors to identify the current quality management practices of MWTP, assess factors affecting concrete quality and study the compliance of material test reports as per standards and finally to propose a framework for quality management practice in concrete. The data collected was analyzed using descriptive statistics. These data were analyzed using spread sheet program and results were analyzed and discussed.

Analysis of the data revealed that quality management practice of Melamchi water treatment plant was well practiced in most cases. The firm had basic elements of quality management system, quality assurance and quality measures followed properly and well managed material storing and testing facilities with few discrepancies found in documentation and test procedure recommended by contract document. The study also shows the project is more focused on quality control and there is lack of feedback system for improvement in quality assurance system.

“Quality of material” was ranked as the most important factor that affects quality of concrete in MWTP. “Cement” was found the most influencing agent for quality fluctuation. The material tests frequencies were incompliance with the requirements in few cases. Because of this, the correlation of cement grade with compressive strength of concrete was found insignificant. Thus, more attention has to be given to proper and timely testing of material as per contractual terms and for approval of material for use, their source and their proper storage.

The uses of quality control/assurance tools were effective. Strict Implementation of formal quality management system would improve the durability and quality of concrete works. It brought to the fore

the need for top management to be involved in concrete works in order to achieve quality concrete and also organize regular training and motivation facilities for professionals involved in concrete works.

Keywords: Quality Control, Quality Assurance, Concrete, Cement, Melamchi Water Treatment

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How to Cite

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Assessment of Household Cement Consumption Pattern in Pokhara Metropolitan City

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Abstract

Cement is the major construction material used in the civil engineering works due to which its demand is very significant. A proper cement brand selection is tough task. Different brands have different pricing and quality, because they are from different origin and industries. The consumers and suppliers of maximum cement market may feel that every brand they are buying and selling are good quality. Most of the cement may confirm the minimum standard for use. The study has been focused to assess consumption of different cement brands available in the Pokhara metropolitan city. To carry out research, cement supplier's data and field data has been collected. Consumers within the study area are considered during the survey. Visual inspection of maximum sites has been done. The different brands of cement in use at site was examined by field survey and analysis was done on SPSS software to obtain results. Maximum cement consumers choose Shivam (30%) in OPC type and Brij cement (25%) in PPC type. During selection of cement consumer are mainly affected by contractors with (35%) without any quality test of cement. 15% of cement consumer don't know about the brand of cement they are using in their household construction. Only 15% consumer consult with engineers for cement selection and quality assurance. 77.50 % consumers don't do quality assurance with engineers during household construction. 70% of cement consumer are unknown about concrete ratio in structural members. 97.5% cement consumer are unaware about manufacturing date. Only 12.50% of cement consumer are affected by advertisement of cements. Positive increasing trend of annual cement consumption is seen from 2070 BS to 2076 BS. Cement consumption forecasting for 2080 BS would be 289942.089 metric ton with upper bound and lower bound consumption 209742.725 metric ton and 370141.450 metric ton respectively. Forecasted cement consumption from RMC suppliers in study area in 2080 BS would be 49125.005 metric ton with upper bound and lower bound consumption 59572.830 metric ton and 38677.190 metric ton respectively.

Keywords: *Cement brands, Visual inspection, fresh and old cement, forecasting, RMC*

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Antimicrobial and Antioxidant Properties of Green Synthesized Nanoparticles Against Food Spoiling Microorganisms

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Abstract

The already existing antimicrobial agents are failing to act on bacteria due to increasing antimicrobial resistance. Green synthesized nanoparticles offer an alternative due to their antimicrobial and antioxidant properties. Copper Nanorods (length 415nm, diameter 50nm), zinc oxide nanoflakes (length 175nm diameter 28nm) and spherical silver nanoparticles (diameter range of 40-45nm) were synthesized using *Coriandum sativum*, *Amomum subulatum*, *Curcuma aromatica* and *Cinnamomum zeylanica* which was confirmed by SEM. The UV, EDX, FTIR also confirmed the successful synthesis, percent weight and groups attached to nanoparticles. The nanoparticles exhibited significant antimicrobial activity against food spoiling bacteria namely, *Clostridium perfringens*, *Staphyococcus aureus* and *Bacillus subtilis* with a maximum zone of inhibition of 1.85cm against *Bacillus* shown by Ag nanoparticles in comparison to 1.58 cm of antibiotic against the same bacteria. The nanoparticles also exhibited antioxidant activity assessed by DPPH assay with significant percent scavenger activity which increased with increase in concentration of nanoparticles. Maximum percent scavenging activity of 94.2 was shown by ZnO nanoparticles at a concentration of 500 μ g/ml. The current work justifies the potential of the green nanoparticles in the present scenario and for future use in food industry or food package industry.

Keywords: *Antimicrobial, Nanoparticles, Antioxidants*

How to Cite

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Building Code-Byelaws Compliance and Cost Assessment of Private Building Construction of Devdaha Municipality

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Abstract

After the devastating earthquake of April 25, 2015 Government of Nepal has legally enforced to implement the National Building Code (NBC) and Byelaws in all the municipalities. The study was carried out to analyze the Building Code-Byelaws Compliance and Cost Assessment of Private Building Construction of Devdaha Municipality.

Primary data were collected from concerned stakeholders-house owners and municipal technical personnel based on a questionnaire survey, key informant interview, focus group discussion and field survey. Secondary data are collected from municipal documents and statistical data published by Municipality. Study of building permit certificates, approved drawings and literature review are also made in order to collect the secondary data. Based on area sampling technique 2 houses per ward were selected by purposive sampling method to check the compliance status of building code and byelaws.

From the study, it is found that, the perspective of concerned stakeholders towards building code and byelaws are positive. Out of 24 households surveyed, only 3 of the buildings have not compiled with the approved drawing whereas 21 buildings byelaws are found to be effectively implemented the approved drawing. The main parameters in which the buildings found non-compliance were plinth area, ground coverage ratio, floor area ratio and setback. The cost of the building constructed without taking approval from the municipality is 24 % less than the building constructed after taking approval. During key informant interview it was said that building construction should comply the building code and byelaws rather than focusing on cost saving which will be vulnerable during natural disasters.

Frequent field inspection, supervision, community awareness comps are the key components to ensure earthquake safer construction. The significance of the study is to enforce the concerned stakeholder to implement the NBC and Byelaws. The samples were limited to building designed by Mandatory rule of thumb(NBC 205: 1994) constructed in the Devdaha Municipality.

Keywords: *NBC, Bylaws, Cost, Compliance, Difference*

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Possibility of Rooftop Rainwater Harvesting – A Case Study of Kathmandu Valley

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Abstract

Rainwater harvesting is a simple, economic and affordable process by which rainwater that collects or falls on roofs, terraces, courtyards and pavements is directed to a storage tank or well which recharges the ground water. Rainwater harvesting is a technique of water conservation and management which helps in minimizing the problem of acute water shortage. The technology of rainwater harvesting is simple and eco-friendly and can be done by anybody with even a little capital. Rainwater harvesting not being a new concept, it ultimately helps to reduce drudgery and hardship of daily life in urban settlements and thus enhance urban development. In the valley, people collect rainwater through downspouts but unfortunately drain to the sewage system which is simply due to lack of awareness of the possibilities that rainwater presents. This shows that in course of modernization and piped water systems, use of rainwater decreased. Now when there is no water in the piped system, then people are again going back to the same point. It is concluded that rainwater harvesting in small or big scale is an important option to get rid of water scarcity.

The overall objective of this study is to evaluate the possibility of promotion of rooftop rainwater harvesting in addressing even increasing water scarcity in Kathmandu, Lalitpur and MadhyapurThimi municipalities. The specific objectives of the proposed study are a) to evaluate the potential of rooftop rainwater harvesting system in supporting domestic and institutional water demand, b) to compare the reduction in domestic and institutional water demand with or without rooftop rainwater harvesting system and c) to evaluate the willingness of the users for adaptation of rooftop rainwater harvesting system in domestic and institutional buildings.

Fifty respondents were taken for questionnaire survey for each municipality. The questionnaire was distributed among friends, relatives, school teachers, publics in hospital and environment exhibitions. They were requested to fill up the questionnaire. Cases of organizations, schools and residences were studied where the rainwater harvesting systems were installed. Interview schedule was carried out with the owner of the houses/schools/organizations where the system was installed. Out of fifty respondents in Kathmandu Metropolitan City, 90% respondents are willing to know about rainwater harvesting system. 52 % respondents already knew about modern rainwater harvesting system. Out of 50 respondents in Lalitpur Metropolitan City, 100% respondents are willing to know about rainwater harvesting system. 52% respondents already know about modern rainwater harvesting system. Out of 50

respondents in MadhyapurThimi Municipality, 100% respondents are willing to know about rainwater harvesting system. 32% respondents already know about modern rainwater harvesting system.

The overall domestic reduction in demand for Kathmandu valley is found to be 24.09% and the overall institutional reduction in demand for Kathmandu valley is found to be 23.99 % which indicates that rainwater harvesting system plays an immense role to reduce water demand to some extent. So, there must be massive campaign to motivate people to install rainwater harvesting systems as we are suffering from maximum water scarcity nowadays. This system can replenish the demands of millions of people of Kathmandu valley. If people start using rainwater harvesting system, then the demand of the people will be fulfilled by rainwater. People will feel relief to some extent. They will be free from paying huge bills for tankers every month because rainwater harvesting system is one time investment. So, it proves to be economical in long run as well. So we must start using rainwater harvesting system for fulfilling our great water demand.

Keywords: *Rainwater, Harvesting, Rooftop, Technical, Economic*

How to Cite

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Recommendation System Using Collaborative Filtering Algorithm for the Movie Recommendations

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Abstract

This is the era of internet and the growth of websites is rapid. The recommendation systems have become the integral part of the information and online market scenario. They are the powerful method for user to enable them access the require information from the large scale of information and products. There have been various research going recently under Collaborative Filtering procedure by which various results have been introduced. Different algorithms are developed and evaluating the performance has been tremendously supported through them. Moreover as we know that number of user are growing rapidly and challenge has been growing to recommendation system. The user always want the one unique data set from the large datasets and he/she don't want to spend any time. In relation to traditional collaborative filtering systems the amount of work increases with the number of participants in the system. The new recommendation systems are always needed which can quickly produce high quality recommendation, no matter how large the problem is. So in this paper I will be addressing the concept of user based and item based collaborative filtering. User- based technique first analyses the similar users matrix to identify relationships between different user and use these relationships to recommend liked item to other user. Item-Based first analyze the user-item matrix to identify relationships between different items and use these relationships to compute recommendations for the user. Vector- Based Similarity is used in both the User- Based and Item-Based technique.

Keywords: *Collaborative filtering, User-Based, Item-Based, Recommendation, Prediction*

How to Cite

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MRI-based Brain Tumor Segmentation using Convolutional Neural Networks

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Abstract

Convolutional Neural Networks are playing a major role in computer vision applications due to their efficiency and accuracy in object segmentation and classification. Due to their high amount of accuracy, they have been implemented in sensitive areas such as analysis of brain MRI images to detect tumor. As faster recognition of Brain tumors plays an important role for further treatment, CNNs are an ideal choice. Here we have implemented deep Convolutional layers using smaller(3X3) convolutional filters to improve the accuracy of the segmentation. Gliomas brain tumor has high heterogeneity in appearance and shape in MRI scans. The training set comprises of High Grade Gliomas(HGG) and Low Grade Gliomas(LGG). Hence, automated tumor segmentation in brain is technically challenging. A lot of algorithms have been made to automate this process, yet this field is still open to research. We built upon existing CNNs for the Brain Tumor Segmentation but with higher performance through the use of VGG. The Convolutional Neural Network comprises of 44 layers. We perform end-to-end training with the last convolution layer with kernel size of 1x1 with softmax activation function for linearity instead of using last layers as fully connected layers to obtain a high resolution output sample which is of high virtue in biomedical image segmentation. The multimodal segmentation approach is used in our research.

Keywords: CNN, 2D, UNet, MRI, Segmentation

How to Cite

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Assessment of Road and Bridge project Performance in terms of Time - Cost

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Abstract

Precise Estimation of Contract duration is a tough job in the construction field given the uncertainties involved in it. The construction industry for Roads and Bridges in Nepal is in a transitional phase where the new technologies are recently introduced but not everyone is in access of it. The methods of works also greatly varies on the individual capacity of each contractor. So, a practical approach is necessary for developing a methodology for contract estimation. With frequent change in regulations regarding extension of time, the need for the accuracy and precision in the estimation of contract duration has even increased more.

This thesis aims at developing an empirical formulae to identify the relation between contract duration and the contract cost based on the data of roads and bridges completed within the last five years. A total of 83 bridges and 78 road projects were analyzed in this thesis to determine a relation between the cost and the time period for these projects. Regression analysis was carried out for developing a mathematical relation. The data was made to fit in Browmillow's time-cost model. As per the regression analysis, 58.3% of variation for data of bridges and 52.5% of variation for data of roads has been incorporated by this model. The obtained equation showed an average deviation of 1.03% for bridge and 2.51% for road data. However, the rate of increase in contract duration decreases with increase in cost. This reason for this is due to the higher level of parallel activities and better use of technologies for the contracts with higher cost.

The trend of EOT for roads and bridges was studied under objective three. Out of 125 bridges and 169 roads studied, 43.17% of bridge and 58.4% of roads required Extension of time. Such extensive percentage of EOT in existing contracts shows our inability for accurate and precise construction duration estimation. Time cost model can be an effective way for estimation of contract duration, for construction. However, the equation requires frequent revision when there is a major change in the inflation/deflation leading to changes in the construction cost over time.

Keywords: *Contract duration, BTC, Time cost model, Time-overrun*

How to Cite

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Building Byelaws and Building Code Compliance in High-rise Apartment Buildings in Kathmandu Valley

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Abstract

Building byelaws and building codes are the two major techno-legal documents to make necessary provisions for planning control, seismic safety, fire safety as well as the the minimum acceptable level of comfort & accessibility in a apartment building. However, the implementation and compliance of building byelaws and building codes in the apartment buildings in Nepal are always questionable. Thus, the overall objective of the study was to assess the building byelaws and building code compliance in apartment buildings. The study has focused on three specific objectives. For the study Primary data were collected by field observation, questionnaire survey and key informants interview. Also the review of existing acts, rules, directives, guidelines, byelaws, codes and other unpublished documents were done for the secondary data. The primary data and secondary data collected were analyzed according to the research framework.

The study revealed that Floor Area Ratio and Allowable Ground Coverage Ratio for apartment buildings in Kathmandu valley are in higher side and the Setbacks, Access Road width and Greenery Open Space for apartment building in Kathmandu valley are in lower side than in Indian context. Allowable ground coverage ratio and floor area ratio for apartment buildings are reasonable in context of Nepal but the greenery open space, setbacks and access road width are needed to be updated to higher value. The major provisions of the building code for Seismic safety of apartment buildings are defined in Nepal National Building Code (NBC) 105:1994 and international codes are also used fulfilling the minimum requirements of the Nepal National Building Code as per NBC 000:1994. The Architectural design parameters, firefighting provisions, provisions of Fire Safety requirements etc. are conformed as per the relevant NBC.

At least eight government authorities are directly involved in the process of approval and building permit process and thus the time taken for approval process is normally more than six months. Department of Urban Development and Building Construction Division office Kathmandu is the main Government authority responsible for supervision and monitoring of apartment building construction. The Municipality and VDC are also responsible for supervision and monitoring of apartment construction. However, other concerned authorities are not made responsible for supervision and monitoring process as per existing acts and rules. There is the provision of third party monitoring system also. Similarly the Use approval to the earthquake damaged apartment is provided after repair, restore and retrofitting work according to the damage category and severity of the damages in structural and nonstructural members.

Though the provisions of byelaws i.e. greenery open space were not complied in four apartments and set back criteria were not complied in two apartments, all other provisions of byelaws were fully complied in all thirteen apartments selected for the study. Likewise most of the provisions of Nepal National Building Code were fully complied in all thirteen apartments selected for the study. However, the RCC bands in masonry infill walls were not provided in all the thirteen selected apartments.

The study revealed that the structural members in **most** of the apartments during the Gorkha earthquake 2015 were damaged minor to moderate only. But the nonstructural infill walls in **most** of the apartments were damaged moderate to severely. The main reason for severe to moderate damage on nonstructural infill walls of apartments, was due to the RCC bands and vertical reinforcement not provided in the nonstructural walls. So the RCC bands shall be provided in masonry infill walls and also the nonstructural masonry infill walls should be replaced in apartment buildings by the light weight, prefabricated materials to avoid the damage in masonry infill walls.

For the effective compliance of the NBC and byelaws in apartments Seismic safety of high rise buildings should be increased in NBC 105:1994 updating the seismic design parameters, building byelaws provisions should be updated for higher value of green open spaces, setbacks and access road. One door procedure should be adopted for approval process to minimize the time for approval process, strict and effective supervision and monitoring mechanism should be introduced in all concerned authorities involved in apartment building approval with sufficient allocation of resources. Effective coordination between all stakeholders and independent third party supervision and monitoring process should be done. Similarly, designer and developer himself should be made fully responsible and accountable for full compliance of building code and building byelaws. Rewards and punishment system should be introduced with level of compliance of the provisions of codes and byelaws. For minimizing the issues raised by the neighbors after Gorkha Earthquake 2015, proper zoning for apartment construction, Seismic vulnerability assessment of the existing apartments and Insurance of Neighbors of the apartments should be done.

Thus, the study revealed that the apartment building construction is a formal housing process regulated by government of Nepal in overall process of approval, supervision and monitoring. The High-rise apartment buildings in Kathmandu valley are safe enough in earthquake, Fire other natural disasters since the compliance of building codes and byelaws is satisfactory. Also there is no option to go for High-rise Apartment buildings in the cities like Kathmandu where the land is very limited.

Keywords: *NBC, Byelaws, Compliance, Apartments, Seismic*

How to Cite

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Quality Management Practice on construction of Suncity Apartment at Kathmandu

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Abstract

Quality management system has been challenging in construction industry. The objective of study was to assess the quality management practice at Construction Site of Suncity Apartment, Goththatar, and Kathmandu, Nepal.

This research was based on lab test of construction material i.e. coarse aggregate, brick, fine aggregate steel, concrete and key informant interview with developers, Consultant, supervisor and engineers, questionnaires survey with clients, and contractors involved in construction projects to access quality management practice following specification, guidelines, codes. Statistical tools like mean value and relative importance index were used for the ranking of different quality methods.

During test of different construction materials at site, the result was found satisfactory for bricks, cement and steel. Similarly the gradation of aggregate was found within the range of specification. Similarly from key informant interview, it was found that different stakeholders have different priorities and preferences. Developers, Clients and contractors give major priority to procurement of equipment & material, quality of the work. Consultants give main priority to work improvement teams. Data and information, benchmarking, levels of output or productivity, desirable results and management commitment and involvement are some important practices to achieve the quality in construction site. This study findings also highlights the major factors affecting the quality management in Suncity Apartment was unavailability of competent staff, low quality drawing and specification and Poor quality procedure and department. the main responsible for ensuring quality assurance practice were to provide training and seminar on quality assurance and support the setting up of quality assurance department in construction firms.

Finally the study showed that various factors that affect the quality construction at Suncity Apartment was quality management practice, quality of construction materials, competent manpower and level of technical guidance. Checklist for the supervision of construction work must be maintained at site for each part of site separately to ensure quality. I would like to acknowledge and express my deepest thanks to all the helping hands.

Key words: *Quality control, Apartment construction, Management practice.*

How to Cite

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SiConSofa - A precast Concrete Block for using Drain and Retention Wall

SiConSofa

Product name: SiConSofa

Applications as:

- (1) Anti-mosquito Drain
- (2) Drain for normal purpose
- (3) Retaining structure
- (4) Slope protection
- (5) Embankment protection

- **Required blocks in unit area** construction = 9.8 nos./m² wall area
- **Nos. of blocks production from 1m³ concrete** = 55 nos.
- **Area coverage by 55 blocks** = 5.6m² area
- **Material cost** = low cost
- **Weight of each block** = 40.5 kg

Award: Bronze medal at 33rd Geneva exhibition

Modular Concrete Blocks:

Modular concrete blocks as per IBS are used as retaining wall without using any mortar to retain earth. This product satisfies the requirement of retaining wall structures. Drain made of precast drain beds and these blocks enhances self-drying through side and bottom seepage during rain as ground water table is quite below especially in summer. Modularity, adaptability, portability, self-interlocking and multipurpose applications are important characteristics of these blocks.

Features:

Performance: Absorbing minor movement due to dry-stacked flexible structure
Cost-effective:

- Dry-stacked without using any mortar
- Use of nominal concrete grade
- Saving installation time and manpower
- Much cheaper than conventional system

Aesthetics:

- Enduring beauty on exposed face

Environmental friendly:

- Elimination of mosquito breeding in drain due to self drying
- User-and environmental-friendly product

Installation:

- Rapid and simple
- 30-35m²/day by 2 workers with simple mechanism

Marketability:

- Saving on material as non-structural component
- Man-days involvement at installation is about one-third of conventional cast-in-situ practice

Drain cum Retaining structure being installed using SiConSofa under Bina Puri Construction S/B

Conventional RC Retaining wall and Drain

Alternative proposal using SiConSofa

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Technology and the Environment – A Framework for a Symbiotic Relationship.

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Abstract

Technology pervades every aspect of modern life and the recent pandemic has increased our reliance on and usage of technology to overcome the constraints of movement that have necessarily been imposed on populations. This has allowed society to proceed with business and social activity via the virtual world. Most of the major advances of society have been driven by technological advances to form new paradigms. These have, though, brought their own problems, with the creation of pollution, waste, depletion of natural resources, exploitation of the workforce and destruction of the natural world. This paper aims considers the requisite changes to use technology to sustain our environment, highlighting the attempts to reverse the destructive trends driven by technological advance. The required contingency framework for technology is discussed, in respect of its central aspects.

The principal theme is that technology, in terms of the creation of tools for human usage, is neutral, however the focus of society in investing in technologies and the manner in which technologies are used is not neutral. The potential for political, social and economic agenda exists, underpinning decisions in these spheres, so human interest drives this technological change. This paper outlines the key themes generating the development of a symbiotic approach to the relationship between technology and the environment.

The requisite change drivers for technology projects are considered, such as the ‘triple bottom line’ approach that encompasses society and the environment together with profit as factors in decision-making and the use of global virtual teams, to run and maintain such projects and their resultant products and services.

The paper uses a review of a range of literature to consider these central themes to enable and encourage technological change that sustains the environment, in respect of the natural and social worlds. A framework is proposed in order to provide an initial consideration of the topic and as a vehicle for future research into this area.

Keywords: *Technology, Environment, Sustainability, Triple Bottom Line, Global Virtual Teams.*

How to Cite

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